

Backsliding Forward? Morocco's New Mudawana Reforms

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Over the past year, Moroccans have watched as state officials have, at the king's behest, discussed and proposed potential revisions to the country's *Mudawanat al-Usra*, or Family Code, often referred to simply as the Mudawana. You may be forgiven for having déjà vu: two decades ago, Morocco was in the news for the same thing.

The 2004 Mudawana reform was a watershed for women's rights in Morocco. While the reform was pushed through by King Mohammed VI just a few years after he ascended the throne, it represented the culmination of more than a decade of mobilization by civil society activists who demanded change. That reform substantially improved women's autonomy and legal standing across several domains, but it also had numerous flaws, which women's rights advocates have been mobilizing to address ever since. These flaws include loopholes undermining the minimum age of marriage (nominally set at 18), challenges limiting divorced women's right to alimony, support, and custody, and the lack of reform to the country's inheritance laws. The new proposed reform tackles several of these issues. At the same time, the first Mudawana reform was contested by Islamist opposition movements, and critics of the reform allege it opened the door to a crisis of divorce and

declining family values in Morocco.

Hanane Darhour (2020) has argued that Morocco's gender quotas for political office have helped legitimize the "de-democratization" of Moroccan political space underway over the past decade. The new Mudawana reform operates similarly. On the one hand, the proposed reforms would represent important gains for women. On the other hand, they will no doubt attract positive international attention to the Moroccan regime for its progressiveness, even as broader political liberties and spaces for democratic contestation in Morocco have continued to decline in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and the victory of palace-linked parties in the 2021 elections. A recent wave of research on women's rights in authoritarian regimes has shown that steps to advance women's rights and political representation often help regimes appease both critics and allies while improving their image among foreign publics (see e.g. Bush et al. 2024, Bjarnegård and Zetterberg 2022, Terman and Byun 2022). Revising the Mudawana now may also be one way the regime seeks to demonstrate its dominance over the Islamist Justice and Development Party (PJD) after the party lost most of its parliamentary seats in 2021. Such a strategy, Tripp (2019) argues, underlined the 2004 reforms, which the regime used to demonstrate

its power over Islamist opposition groups.

Beyond legitimizing de-democratization, this dynamic of reform in Morocco may have another unintended consequence. Elsewhere (Barnett 2023), I argue that Morocco's earlier reforms demonstrate one way that the politics of women's rights may exacerbate conservative lag, or the tendency for people to think that society remains more conservative than it is. I argue that the increased salience of vocal conservative minorities during periods of contested women's rights reforms can feed into conservative lag as the virulent opposition of a few may garner disproportionate attention. In the case of Morocco, the regime positioning itself as the "savior" of women may also have reinforced perceptions that only an autocratic hand can advance gender equality in the face of an intractably conservative public. I further argue that such perceptions have consequences: for example, a narrative that laws are out of sync with social norms may undermine officials' willingness to enforce the laws on the books.

With the new Mudawana reforms, the advance of women's rights in Morocco may once again paradoxically reinforce perceptions that support for gender equality is weaker than it is. For example, both former PJD prime ministers have made headlines in recent months decrying the potential reforms, with Abdelilah Benkirane even threatening to mobilize a new million-person march (Rahhou 2024).

Even as the new Mudawana reforms would be step forward for women on paper, they are also a step back in two broad senses: (1) reaffirming the power and centrality of the monarchy to politics in Morocco in general and to women's rights specifically; and (2) recentering public discourse around the conserva-

tive opposition against which these reforms advance—potentially undermining prospects for the law's implementation. ♦

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